

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) Technology for Vulnerable Road Users' (VRU) Safety on Hilly Roads

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Abstract

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Abstract Summary

- ❖ This research aims to improve vulnerable road users' (VRU) safety at “blind spots” presented by roads built on hills with steep grade.
- ❖ Two-node Mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) and Vehicular ad-hoc Network (VANET) antenna configurations are considered within a computer simulation.
- ❖ The objective is to inform the application of a physical antenna test bed that may be used to develop emerging V2X crash avoidance technologies in potentially hazardous driving environments.

Abstract Summary

- ❖ Single omnidirectional dipole antennas and 2 X 2 MIMO antenna arrays are placed and tested in separate simulations for 5°, 10°, and 15° hills.
- ❖ Power transmitted by V2X antennas and pedestrian smart-phone antennas in an uphill driving scenario are observed within a range of 60 meters.
- ❖ A minimum of -70 dBm power received at the VRU smart-phone antenna from the V2X antenna and vice versa is sufficient to verify that this simulation data may adequately assist in physical applications of crash avoidance.

Abstract Summary

This project differs from our previous V2X simulation research for pedestrian safety for two reasons:

1. The latest versions (2024) of the Altair Feko, Wallman, and Proman (Winprop) software are utilized.
2. Antenna performance is observed in a strictly Non-Line-of-Sight (NLOS) scenario on hilly roads.

Introduction

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Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X)

- ❖ V2X refers to wireless communication systems that allow vehicles to connect with entities in their surroundings.
- ❖ According to the IEEE, V2X enables vehicles to communicate with other vehicles (V2V), roadside infrastructure (V2I), pedestrians (V2P), networks (V2N), and the power grid (V2G).
- ❖ V2X allows vehicles to gather more information about their surroundings for safety, traffic efficiency, and autonomous driving purposes.

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X)

C. McNerny, H. Burt, Rizab, Maturj, "Enabling Safer Crosswalks with Smart Vehicle-to-Everything Technology," 2024 51st Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF), Glassboro, New Jersey, United States, June 2024.

MANET and VANET

Fig. 1: Architecture of MANET and VANET.

Hussein, Nehad & Yaw, Chong Tak & Koh, Siaw Kiang & Siang, Kok. (2022). A Comprehensive Survey on Vehicular Networking: Communication Applications, Challenges, and Upcoming Research Directions. *IEEE Access*. 10(1), 1-16. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3198656.

West 28th Street and University Avenue

An image from Google Maps of West 28th Street approaching a four-way intersection on University Avenue in Little Rock, Arkansas, United States.

Lineof-Sight (LOS)

C. McNerny, H. Burt-Rizzo, Matur, "Enabling Safer Crosswalks with Smart Vehicle-Everything Technology," 2024 51st Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF), Glassboro, New Jersey, United States, June 2024

NonLineof-Sight (NLOS)

S.Biddleston, K. Redmill, M. Lucic and Ü. Ozguner, "An Integrated 802.11p WAVE DSRC and Vehicle Traffic Simulator With Experimentally Validated Urban (LOS and NLOS) Propagation Models", *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, no. 4, pp. 1702, Dec. 2012

Altair FEKO and WinProp software

- ❖ Altair FEKO is electromagnetic simulation software used to model realistic radio frequency propagation patterns.
- ❖ Altair WinProp is a software focused on the propagation and interaction of electromagnetic waves based on SBR (shooting and bouncing rays).
- ❖ These softwares enable engineers to analyze far-field radiation patterns, impedance mismatch, and coupling within the context of key antenna performance environments.

IEEE 802.11p

- ❖ IEEE 802.11p is an amendment of the IEEE 802.11 standard to include Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE).
- ❖ It is the current IEEE standard used by Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) applications in the 5.9 GHz (5.85-5.925 GHz) band.
- ❖ This standard is anticipated to expand into 6G as data transmission rates increase and new communication technologies emerge.

Methods

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Design of Simulations

- ❖ This study considers 28 GHz fixed frequency antenna performance on hills with dimensions provided on the following slide.
- ❖ Each hill is angled at 5° (8.75% grade), 10° (17.63% grade), and 15° (26.8% grade).
- ❖ 3D models of each hill and plateau are generated in Blender, an open-source polygon modeling software [3], and imported as .blend files into Altair Wallman.

Longitude, Latitude, Height, and Slope Dimensions of Hills in Meters

	X	Y	Z	Slope
5°	29.89 m	10.00 m	2.61 m	30.00 m
10°	29.54 m	10.00 m	5.21 m	30.00 m
15°	28.98 m	10.00 m	7.76 m	30.00 m

Table. 1. Dimensions, generalized for a lane and median width of highway.

Fig. 2. 3Dmodel of 5° hill and plateau with dimensions.

Fig. 3. 3Dmodel of 10° hill and plateau with dimensions.

Fig. 4. 3Dmodel of 15° hill and plateau with dimensions.

3D view in PROMAN of the road plateau with pedestrian and vehicle antennas.

3D view of the simulation from the perspective of the VRU antenna placed approximately 1 meter above the plateau.

3D view of the simulation from the perspective of the V2X antenna placed approximately 2 meters above the ground plane.

TABLE. III 5G NR OPERATING FREQUENCIES IN FR2 BANDS

Band	Range of frequencies in FR2			
	Uplink [GHz]	Downlink [GHz]	Bandwidth [MHz]	Duplex Mode
n257	26.5- 29.5	26.5- 29.5	50-400	TDD
n258	24.25- 27.5	24.25- 27.5	50-400	TDD
n259	39.5- 43.5	39.5- 43.5	50-400	TDD
n260	37.0- 40.0	37.0- 40.0	50-400	TDD
n261	27.5-28.35	27.5-28.35	50-400	TDD

28 GHz Dipole Antenna Far Field (Altair Feko)

28 GHz Dipole Antenna Power (Altair Feko)

Fine Polygon Meshing

- These far field radiation patterns are computed using a standard Method of Moments (MoM) computation with fine polygon meshing applied to the dipole antennas.

Results

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Simulation Overview

- ❖ The dominant path model (DPM) is used in our simulations to determine the dominant path between the transmitter and each receiver pixel.
- ❖ DPM is chosen because the computation time, compared to ray tracing, is significantly reduced with nearly identical results.
- ❖ The Single input Single-output (SISO) and Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) antenna array far-field propagation patterns are tested and analyzed at 28 GHz with 30 dBm of power applied.

SISO - 5° Hill

SISO - 10° Hill

SISO - 15° Hill

MIMO - 5° Hill

MIMO - 10° Hill

MIMO - 15° Hill

Air Interface (PROMAN)

Edit Project Parameter - fivedegreeMIMO

Air Interface | Simulation | Traffic | Network | Propagation | Sites | Components | Database | Computation

Multiple Access
 OFDM / SOFDMA [Settings]

Duplex Separation
 Duplex FDD [Settings]

MIMO Technology
 MIMO 2 Streams [Settings]

Bandwidth
 Channel Bandwidth 5000 kHz

Carriers

T	ID	Frequency...	Frequency...
S	1	28000.00 ...	28000.00 ...

[Add] [Combine] [Delete] [Edit]

Transmission Modes (MCS)
 Sort position (up)

Name	P...	Data Rat...	Data Rat...
------	------	-------------	-------------

[Add] [Delete] [Edit]

Cell Assignment
 Highest Rx power of all carriers in the network
 Definition of min. required SNIR
 Min. required SNIR 3 dB

Mobile Station / Subscriber Station
 [Settings]

Repeaters
 Number of Multihops 0
 Min. required Rx power at repeater -150 dBm

[OK] [Cancel]

- The Air Interface in PROMAN is used for arranging the MIMO 2 Stream array at separate 28 GHz carrier frequencies with OFDM / SOFDMA (Downlink and Uplink)
- Duplex: FDD (Frequency-Division Duplexing) is enabled for a theoretical 5 MHz bandwidth.
- This configuration is used to prevent user-error when placing antenna arrays.

Conclusion

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Conclusion

Based on the observations of this study, there is quantifiable overlap between the transmitted power of V2X and VRU point-source dipole antennas operating in the 28 GHz frequency band for single omnidirectional dipole antennas and 2 X 2 MIMO configurations.

Sufficient data is presented in this simulation to verify and reinforce environment-aware antenna applications and suggest locations for the installation of repeaters or relays in existing Vehicle to Everything (V2I) systems to service potentially hazardous NLOS hill scenarios in C-V2X systems.

Conclusion

Valuable insights into the potential performance of V2X communication systems in challenging NLOS environments are provided by these computations that may be applied to more realistic scenarios.

Computational complexity is kept to a minimum in this study to address gaps in the technical literature where these types of simulations are mainly observed at a macro scale.

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Questions?

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Thank you for your time!